

CULTURAL SCIENCES

ANALYTICAL TOOLS OF NEURAL NETWORKS AND IMMERSIVE SOLUTIONS IN OPTIMIZING COMMUNICATION PROCESSES

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Abstract

The article is dedicated to exploring the possibilities of modern neural network technologies and immersive solutions for analyzing and optimizing communication processes. Key tools based on artificial intelligence are examined, which allow for the effective processing of large volumes of data, uncovering hidden patterns, and predicting audience behavior. Special attention is given to the application of neural networks and immersive technologies for reputation monitoring, content personalization, and managing interactions with target groups. The article also discusses the advantages and challenges of implementing such technologies in communication practices, as well as the prospects for their further use.

Keywords: neural networks, communications, artificial intelligence, social media, immersiveness, data processing

Introduction.

Modern technologies based on neural networks optimize communication approaches, providing users with new opportunities for analysis, creation, support, and transformation of messages, thereby increasingly personalizing and improving them in the processes of information exchange. Contemporary neural network solutions not only automate routine operations – such as creating texts, images, and multimedia materials – but also conduct deep analysis of the behavior of target audience groups, revealing hidden patterns of interaction and predicting trends based on heterogeneous information.

This makes communication strategies more targeted and effective, and the decision-making process more informed and rational, based on objective data. More and more companies and specialists are implementing neural network tools in their advertising, PR and marketing strategies, which allows not only to save resources, but also to obtain valuable analytical results for the further development of communications.

Concepts and types of neural network technologies in communications.

Since 2010, the era of neural networks, artificial intelligence (AI), and machine learning has begun to develop actively. From this time onwards, the technology is capable of performing complex tasks and making autonomous decisions, becoming more automatic and gradually removing humans from social processes, transitioning to a post-social stage of the evolution of managed systems [1, p.75].

Although research on neural networks and AI was conducted in the mid-20th century, when in 1956 at a conference in Dartmouth (USA) scientists J. McCarthy, N. Wiener, and M. Minsky demonstrated the capabilities of machine intelligence, it was this concept that found its wide application in 2021. The term 'artificial intelligence' was proposed at a scientific seminar of the same name at Dartmouth College (USA) in 1956 [2, c. 16]. At the same time, in 1957, an attempt was made to

develop a system (perceptron) by researcher F. Rosenblatt that could imitate the workings of the human eye with the brain.

Today, AI technologies are actively being integrated into various spheres of life, maintaining a steady growth in their application across the broadest areas of human activity. Let's focus on the main concepts and definitions, and analyze the key aspects of the topic of interest for preliminary understanding. A neural network (hereinafter referred to as NN) is a mathematical model that simulates the work of neural cells in the human brain. It consists of numerous "neurons" that process data and the connections between them. Each neuron receives input data, processes it, and passes the results to the next neuron. Through training, an NN can recognize patterns, solve problems, create images, videos, audio – in other words, mimic the activity of the human brain [3, p.43].

Artificial intelligence is a broad area of computer technology aimed at creating systems capable of performing tasks that traditionally require human intelligence. Such tasks include understanding speech, making decisions, learning, and adapting. AI includes various methods and technologies, among which neural networks are one of the key components. In addition to neural networks, AI uses machine learning, logical programming, algorithms, and other approaches to automate and improve processes in various fields. [3, p. 44].

Therefore, AI is a broader term that encompasses any system capable of performing tasks comparable to human intelligence, whereas AN is a specific type of AI used for processing complex datasets. [4].

Thus, NN are complex models built on the ability to process large volumes of data and generate new data based on them. Therefore, they are also called 'generative neural networks' [5, p.9].

Today, NS are perceived in accordance with the concept of "augmented intelligence" [6] as a model of partnership between humans and AI, in which AI enhances human cognitive abilities, helping to learn,

make decisions, and master new skills. Augmented intelligence differs from the automated and auxiliary levels in that it does not simply perform routine operations or optimize decisions, but actively helps to find the best solutions in specific conditions, using machine and augmented learning methods. It acts as a tool for ex-

panding human intelligence, rather than replacing humans, while maintaining human control and participation in the decision-making process.

Therefore, the areas in which neural networks outperform humans differ from those in which creativity, emotional intelligence, and complex thinking are important. Some areas and their differences are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Ratio of areas of activity in which neural networks are superior and inferior to humans

Areas where neural networks outperform humans	Areas where neural networks cannot compete with humans
Processing and analysis of large volumes of data	Ethical judgments and moral decisions
Recognition of images, faces, objects	Emotional intelligence and contextual awareness
Diagnosis of diseases	Interpersonal communication and negotiation skills
Automate routine and repetitive tasks	Strategic thinking and complex decision making
Forecasting market trends and consumer behavior	Intuition and non-standard (creative) solutions
Natural language processing (translation, text generation)	Conflict management and people motivation
Optimizing processes and increasing productivity	Cultural understanding and adaptation in complex social situations
Creating realistic content in games and entertainment	Creative art and deep philosophical reflection

Successful life in the modern world requires strong, versatile professionals with interdisciplinary knowledge and skills. It is these specialists, who are called "T-shaped" people, who are able to effectively solve complex problems, quickly adapt to changes and work at the intersection of different fields. The vertical line of the letter "T" symbolizes deep expertise in one specific area, and the horizontal line symbolizes a broad outlook, the ability to interact with representatives of other professions and use knowledge from related disciplines. This approach allows not only to achieve high results in your profession, but also to find non-standard solutions, integrating experience from different fields of activity.

The term "T-shaped person" was proposed by American IBM employee Jim Sporer to describe the cognitive profile of a person who possesses both broad and deep knowledge, i.e. a person who is capable of acquiring deep knowledge in several areas during his life [7, p. 35].

Such a specialist can cope not only with highly specialized tasks, but is also able to effectively discuss with experts from other fields, quickly master new skills and adapt to changes. Due to this, such T-shaped specialists are especially in demand in interdisciplinary and hybrid teams, where a combination of deep expertise and breadth of knowledge is required to solve complex problems and improve overall efficiency. Understanding the work of neural networks and AI, as well as using the skills to work with them for such specialists, this professional add-on enhances their qualification characteristics in the communications sphere.

There are several main types of neural networks that are applied in communications [8, p.29]:

- feedforward neural networks – transmit information sequentially from the input to the output layer without feedback. They are often used in combination with other types of networks to solve classification and forecasting problems;

- convolutional neural networks – specialize in processing visual information. Due to their architecture, which includes convolutional and pooling layers, they are successfully used for image recognition, video analysis and natural language processing, which is important for visual and multimedia content in communications;

- recurrent neural networks – have the ability to process sequential data, taking into account the context of previous elements. This makes them indispensable when working with texts, speech and other time series, which allows you to create chatbots, machine translation systems and text generation. In addition, generative models are actively used in communications, capable of creating new texts, images, and audio content based on training data, which expands the possibilities for creative content and automation of communication processes.

Analytical tools based on neural networks.

The implementation of neural network analytical tools in the field of communications allows organizations to significantly improve the quality and effectiveness of both internal and external interactions. Using neural networks, many communication processes are optimized due to deep analysis of large volumes of data, which includes information about the organization's structure, vertical and horizontal interaction channels, details about clients and employees, distribution of responsibilities, and the timeliness of their execution. This approach allows for the identification of hidden patterns in the behavior of employees and clients, as well as taking their preferences into account. This paves the way for more precise audience segmentation and the formation of personalized communication strategies that consider the characteristics of each group or even individual.

Modern neural network solutions make it possible to automatically create customized messages and offers, which significantly increases user engagement and loyalty. AI-based tools such as ChatGPT, Midjourney,

Kandinsky, Sora, etc. are used to generate targeted emails, advertising texts, and scripts for chatbots, which allows you to quickly and effectively build a dialogue with the target audience. In addition, analytical tools of neural networks and AI allow you to analyze the tonality and emotional coloring of messages, which is important for reputation monitoring and assessing audience reactions. This allows you to identify bursts of activity or negative trends and quickly respond to crisis situations.

Immersiveness of communications.

Immersiveness is understood as the property of content or technology that creates the effect of deep immersion of the user in an artificially created environment through the impact on their senses. The term comes from the English word «immerse», which means «to delve into». [9].

According to Professor of Marketing at the Kellogg School of Management at Northwestern Univer-

sity in the USA, F. Kotler, an immersive period of technology is coming, when communications will be based on «digital and multisensory interaction that will create a more memorable and engaging customer experience» [10, p.29].

The integration of AI with virtual, augmented, and mixed reality technologies makes communication not only visually and audibly rich but also maximally interactive, personalized, and flexible. Immersiveness allows for the creation of a sense of complete presence and deep user engagement in the digital space. Thanks to NN, sound processing, gesture recognition, and content generation become more natural, emotionally rich, and closer to real communication.

F. Kotler believes that five elements of experience are necessary for complete immersion: multisensory, interactive, participatory experience, frictionless interaction experience, and storytelling experience. (tab. 2) [10, p.70-71].

Table 2

Elements of immersiveness and their characteristics

№	Element of experience	Characteristics
1	Multisensory	Stimulates the senses (sight, hearing, smell, taste, and touch), helps to attract attention.
2	Interactive	Suggests a two-way dialogue.
3	Experience of participation	Designed for active client engagement (meetings, greetings, etc.).
4	Experience of problem-free interaction	Ease and smoothness for clients in choosing and purchasing goods/services. Absence of defects, technical malfunctions, and friction during interaction.
5	Experience in storytelling	The integration of all elements into a single narrative, creating an immersive experience for the customer. Connecting and encouraging communication with the brand.

Such digital points and a hybrid approach to communications based on NS and AI allow to create a feeling of full presence and emotional response from the user. In educational, professional and creative spheres, immersive communications based on NS and AI open up new horizons of knowledge, development of necessary skills, conducting joint discussions and presentations in a virtual environment. These technologies not only increase the efficiency of information transfer, but also contribute to the emergence of new formats of interaction, in which the line between the physical and digital environments is erased.

Prospects for the development of analytical tools of neural networks in communications.

The future of neural network technologies in communications is related to their further integration with Big Data, the Internet of Things (IoT), and other innovations. More advanced AI models are expected to emerge, expanding the capabilities of multimedia content generation and enhancing personalization. Digital communication technologies possess open multimedia, multichannel capabilities, providing visual presence and participation in open dialogue. Digital intercultural communication, utilizing social networks and messengers, will simplify the issue of language barriers, accelerate information exchange, and expand the audience. Therefore, the dynamics of technological progress will ensure the emergence of new professions in communications, such as media buyer, neuro-illustrator, prompt engineer, AI trainer, content creator, and others.

Inspired (viral) communications combined with immersive technologies based on neuro-network and AI can significantly enhance user engagement. Viral content, thanks to its emotional richness and ability to spread quickly through interpersonal channels, will continue to stimulate audience participation in marketing projects. For this, immersive technologies, such as virtual and augmented reality, will create a sense of complete immersion, making interactions with brands more interactive and memorable. Mixing such approaches will not only capture the user's attention but also retain it, forming a deep emotional connection and increasing brand loyalty. Also, an important direction will be the development of ethical standards and regulation of the use of neuro-networks in the communication field.

However, the introduction of neural network-based analytical tools into communications, as well as the use of inspired (viral) and immersive technologies, may introduce significant risks to humans. One of these risks is social isolation and deterioration of live communication skills. With frequent interaction with AI, people, especially vulnerable groups (children, adolescents, people in crisis situations, as well as those who need emotional or psychological support, etc.), may prefer virtual communication, which will lead to alienation and a decrease in the quality of interpersonal relationships.

In addition, immersive technologies are capable of creating deep dives and virtual worlds, which sometimes leads to psychological dependence and distortion of reality perception. Thus, according to WHO estimates, mental disorders continue to occupy a leading position in modern medicine, about 300 million people worldwide live with depression and about 260 million suffer from anxiety disorders [11].

Virtual and immersive environments create a “looping effect” [12]. This term was introduced by the Canadian philosopher I. Hacking. The scientist associates this effect and its manifestation in the context of human interaction with virtual and immersive technologies that transform their perception and behavior. For example, immersion in virtual worlds and constant use of immersive tools can change self-perception, form new behavior patterns, and even influence the user’s identity. Thus, a person becomes a “moving target” that changes under the influence of technologies that were originally created to study or influence their functions. This enhances the feedback effect between the user and the technology, which is important to consider when developing and implementing immersive systems.

Users are becoming overly dependent on virtual content and assistants, which has a negative impact on their mental health and communications. It is becoming difficult to identify fixed roles or unambiguous interpretations in communications, as the participant and the technology are in a state of constant change. Virtual and immersive environments enhance the effect by immersing the user in interactive scenarios where the boundaries between the sender and receiver of the message are blurred, and the interaction becomes more complex and multi-layered. This approach requires considering not only the content of the messages, but also the emotional, cognitive and social changes that occur during the communication process.

Analytical neural networks, when generating information, do not always guarantee its accuracy, which increases the risk of dissemination of unreliable data and manipulation. This is especially dangerous when it comes to making important decisions based on such data.

There is also a security threat associated with the possible leakage of users' personal data. Neural network systems can become a target for cyberattacks, including targeted distortion of training data, which will lead to failures in operation and serious consequences. In the economic sphere, AI-based automation can lead to job losses and cause social instability.

Viral technologies, by distributing emotionally charged content, are capable of causing mass behavior and manipulating consciousness, and immersive technologies enhance this effect, reducing critical thinking and increasing addiction. All this requires a careful and responsible approach to the implementation of such technologies, taking into account ethical and legal standards, as well as measures to protect users and support their mental and socio-cultural well-being.

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